

IMPROVING THE PRIMARY PREVENTION OF ACUTE DIARRHEAL DISEASES AMONG CHILDREN

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Annotation

The educational program for between schools, academic Liceums of professional colleges for perfection of propagation of a healthy image of life and increase of sanitary culture for preventive maintenance sharp Diarrhoea of diseases among children is developed. The inclusion of educational hours on all age categories in the fourth quarter is offered, as the season illnesses sharp Diarrhoea by diseases basically begins in middle of May.

Key word

diarrhoea, prophylaxis, school, college, students.

As you know, health depends on the characteristics of the adequate development of the body. Currently, the following criteria for health have been proposed: the optimal level of physical, neuromuscular and mental development; the adequate level of functional and social adaptation in a child; the ability to strongly resist adverse effects (optimal immunno-biological reactivity); premorbid conditions with symptoms of chronic diseases and the absence of diathesis [6].

Disease prevention or prevention, is a system of social, hygienic and medical activities carried out by the state to maintain the health of the population and prevent diseases [2]. At the moment, 3 different variations of prevention are distinguished: primary prevention is the protection against the negative impact of natural, productive, domestic, social spheres, unfavorable factors on human health, in which pathological changes in healthy people can be called [1;4]. Secondary prevention is the early detection of a disease, the relapse of which is a system of measures aimed at the development of a pathological process and the Prevention of the appearance of complications. Tertiary prevention is a system of measures for the Prevention of disability and social rehabilitation. In the Republic of Uzbekistan, which is among the regions with a hot climate, there is a decrease in the incidence

of acute infectious Ichthyological diseases, but the incidence remains high among children [3;7].

The purpose of the study: the goal of our scientific research work carried out is to improve the developed primary prevention of acute diarrheal diseases among children.

Materials and methods of research: To do this, the recommendations developed by the World Health Organization, the Health Organization of the Republic of Uzbekistan for the Prevention of acute diarrheal diseases are to perfect our region in accordance with the geographical climatic social specific lifestyle. The reason is that the developed recommendations and guidelines are the same for all segments of the population, which lies in the complexity of taking into account the customs, lifestyle, national and local characteristics of the local population.

In order to improve the work of raising sanitary culture and promoting a healthy lifestyle among children with high efficiency, which is considered convenient in children's institutions (kindergartens, secondary education schools, academic lyceums and vocational colleges), we developed a special program for inclusion in the educational programs of high school lyceums and colleges as extracurricular studies.

Research results. The program was divided into three sections, differing in age depending on the ability to receive information given to schoolchildren by them:

- 1.Children of small school age-grades 1-4 (from 7 to 12 years old).
- 2.Children of senior school age-grades 5-9 (from 12 to 15 years old).
- 3.Academic Lyceum and vocational colleges-grades 10-12 (ages 15 to 18).

The subject program proposed for inclusion in school curricula for children of junior school age (grades 1-4) is as follows:

1.Diarrheal diseases. Their species. Frequent seasons. Reasons for Origin. Examples of the call of disease of various causes. Causes that cause diarrheal diseases among schoolchildren.

2.Oral transmission of the disease. Transmission through food products. The path of transmission of disease from a sick child to a healthy child. The ways of transmission of this disease from adults to children.

3.The main manifestations of the disease, the disease is the state of the body (the use of antibiotics pala-parting and, as a result, anemia, the occurrence of dysbacteriosis). Measures to prevent diarrheal diseases.

4. Schedule to prevent the disease, show pictures, videos, organize games of all kinds and test the knowledge received by children.

When drawing up these topics, children were taken at the expense of their mental development and the level of knowledge given in school and family. They expand the worldview of children of this age, increase their medical knowledge and sanitary culture, and reduce the incidence of various diarrheal diseases.

The topics recommended for inclusion in the curriculum of children of senior school age (grades 5-9) are in harmony with the topics of Biological Sciences in the high school program, depending on their ability to receive information:

1. Diarrheal diseases. Their species. Reasons for Origin. The concept of causative agents. The development of bacteria, spread among school children.

2. The route of oral transmission of diarrheal diseases. Transmission through food, fruit and vegetables, transmission into the body of healthy children, transmission routes from adults to children.

3. Diarrheal diseases are the main clinical manifestations, course, changes in the body, types of diarrhea, the concept of who to resort to when diarrhea occurs.

4. Necessary activities for the Prevention of diarrheal diseases. Necessary measures to be taken in order to avoid the occurrence of diarrheal diseases in the classroom or at home, to give him first aid, to avoid transmission to others.

Total topics are 4 academic hours, of which 3 hours are held in the form of a lecture using visual aids and other teaching tools, and the last push-up lesson is held in the form of practical training so that students can consolidate the knowledge gained.

For Academic High School and vocational colleges, the proposed program is more perfect and differs from the topics in the structured program above in the abundance of information, the fullness of training, the excess of volume.

1. The concept of diarrheal diseases. Spread among the world population and in our Republic. The influence of social and environmental factors that cause diarrheal diseases. Ways to spread the disease among school children.

2. Variations of constipation. Diseases caused by microorganisms. Diarrhea is an understanding of disease-causing bacteria. Their difference from each other. Structure of bacteria.

3. Causes, factors that cause diarrheal diseases. Transmission routes (by mouth, communication-household, food, fruit-carrots). The fall of disease-calling bacteria into the body of healthy children, the changes that will occur in the body.

4. Manifestation of diarrheal diseases. Symptoms of diarrheal diseases and first aid. To whom to apply, provide first aid until the arrival of a medical officer.

5. Measures to prevent diarrheal diseases, finding ways of transmission, isolating the patient. Give examples of the same topic and solve situational issues.

6. Strengthen the acquired knowledge using a special visual chart, slide, video files.

This proposed program is equivalent to 6 academic hours, of which 5 hours are held in the form of lectures that sum up information on various ichthetar diseases, and the last hour as a practical exercise to consolidate knowledge on the topics covered, which includes a test, a situational issue, practical games. We believe that it is better to include the hours of classes held in all age groups in the fourth quarter program. The reason is that the season of infection with acute diarrheal or ichthetar diseases begins in mid-May.

Conclusions. Thus, we found that the newly developed programs for primary prevention of ichthetar diseases should be carried out among children living in this region, namely in kindergartens, schools, academic lyceums and vocational colleges. Because acute diarrheal diseases, especially more prevalent among children, are considered to have reproductive characteristics. It would also be the same if the topics in these programs were also promoted among young mothers, since their role in the spread of acute diarrheal diseases among children is important.

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